

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Loquet

FIRST NAME: Wim

PROGRAM CODE: MNRJ-R

COURSE CODE: ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
 The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
 The author did use Zotero to insert references
 The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)
 The author used the following software: Microsoft Office Home on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 1–4)
2. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 5–13)
3. Rules of thumb for writing papers (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14–22)
4. Style guides (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 24)
5. American versus British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 27–34)
6. Chicago style (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 56–61)
7. Useful Tools (EUCLID 2021, Top Tip Bio 2021, and EUCLID 2015)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING BASICS AND TOOLS

1) INTRODUCTION

About 20 years ago, I started my career and have not written specific articles or papers since. I am convinced that this course will refresh, even expand, my knowledge and skills, which will enable me to write at a consistently decent level. My career path has been mainly technical, from field operations to operations manager level.

I recently resigned to make a career change from oil and gas into renewable energy, actively contributing to a better future. This program will be invaluable to ensure the best new start possible. English is not my first language; however, this should not hold me back as I have been working in English speaking countries for several years. I find it very useful to have this course before starting the specific renewable energy courses.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The first chapter from this course that jumps out and is of great value for me is essay writing. Not only does it give a clear step by step overview of how to structure and write an essay, but also clearly guides on how to plan, research, organize, write, and edit

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any essay before sending it in. On page four of the same documents, we can find a great checklist to ensure we did not omit anything and confirm we obeyed all the rules.

ACA-401/ACA-401D [coursepack for period one](#) mentions that "Although there are some basic steps to writing an assignment, essay writing is not a linear process. You might work through the different stages a number of times in the course of writing an essay." (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 1)

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3) PLAGIARISM

The second highlight for me is the detailed explanation of plagiarism and avoiding any sort of it. These pages provide a clear overview of how we can credit the original author by mentioning the source and citing it, including in-text citations and the works cited list. This list is also called 'bibliography' or the 'references'.

The studied pages also give directions on integrating quotations, depending on the length, and guide what to do when we wish to alter the quoted text. The pages also provide extra attention to paraphrasing, saying the same as an author but with our own words, while we still refer to the source in this case.

"When to Give Credit to Author? When using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source." (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 5)

4) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

The rules of thumb for writing papers go over what we should and should not do while writing an essay and where to pay extra attention to avoid making mistakes. These pages will surely guide me in writing the response papers and probably even more when doing the thesis.

The literature review, page 17 and onwards, details the frequently made mistakes and clarifies when to use which words, including exceptions to the rules, use of spaces, the difference between "that" and "which", the use of the comma, when we should write a number out and when we should use the numeral version, and so on.

"When you finish writing, read your paper out loud. Writing that does not sound right will not read right." (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 16)

5) STYLE GUIDES

The fifth chapter from this course elaborates on style guides, what they are, and why we use them. This chapter opened new areas of writing to me, and it explained clearly

all the different aspects to be taken into consideration when writing to ensure consistency. I will apply the Chicago Rules (Turabian) as [EUCLID](#) recommends from now on.

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"A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting." (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 24)

The style is invaluable for any writer to maintain consistency when writing multiple papers. When working on a document with other writers, all colleagues must apply the same style, so the final document becomes a single piece rather than a collation of bits and pieces. Also, when writing for a specific company, magazine, or newspaper, it is crucial to follow their particular style requirements.

6) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

The sixth chapter of this course explains the significant differences between American and British English. There are several reasons why American English has encountered a wider spread internationally than British English, including but not limited to population, the wealth of the economy, magnitude of mass media, and so on. Worth noting is that both American and British English are variants of World English, which causes them to be very similar, yet with several slight differences.

From page 27 onwards, we find a clear overview of the differences categorized by the same or a different pronunciation and spelling. Some terms have a different spelling, pronunciation or even have an extra or other meaning.

The chapter also pointed out the different use of plurals, which was new to me. It also highlighted some of the words American English uses compared to British English for the same items and some creative spin-offs, listed on page 30 onwards.

"Smoke/fog = smog; cf. cosmetics/pharmaceuticals = cosmeceuticals; pharmaceuticals/farming = pharming" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 31)

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The authors also explain [ethnic words](#), cultural references, regional variations, stereotyping, etc. What is also remarkable is the difference in punctuation and the writing of dates between American and British English, which will undoubtedly confuse if the writer does not maintain the style and language throughout the document.

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7) CHICAGO STYLE

Chapter 8: CMS Crib Sheet informs us of the Chicago style and the rules to apply when using this style. It explains when we can or should not use abbreviations and when to use capitalization or not.

The authors also elaborate on when and how to use compound words, italics, quotation marks, numbers. Page 48 emphasizes that we should use the Standard American format (October 8, 2021) in the future.

Quotations should also follow strict rules, including correcting errors and permitted changes or editing, block quotations and how to apply depending on the size of the quote.

Chicago style also dictates a specific Page format, being 8 ½ by 11 inches, and we need to leave a margin of at least 1 inch on all edges of the page. The suggested font is Times Roman with twelve-point type for text and ten-point for notes. One-half inch applies to all indents. Chicago style also has specific rules for the particular weight of the papers to be used, alignment, spacing, and page numbering.

Footnotes, headings, tables, notes, endnotes, and bibliographies also have their specific rules to follow under the Chicago style, as explained on pages 50 and onwards.

"The CMS Crib Sheet is one of a family of style guides available at www.docstyles.com." (Cleenerwerck & Gulma 2021, 44)

As mentioned before, the style subject is new to me, and this chapter will be of immense value to me as I will be able to get back to these pages to ensure compliance.

8) USEFUL TOOLS

It is not a chapter in the pdf document provided. However, I would like to elaborate on my thoughts and give feedback on the suggested tools for the course as I feel they are adding a lot of value to my experience and quality.

First, I followed the chronological order of the assigned study material to explore these valuable tools, which are both new to me. I knew about Grammarly thru an ad when watching YouTube videos to broaden my knowledge on renewable energy; however, I never used the application. Zotero, on the other hand, is new to me.

The first training video on Zotero gave a good introduction and guidelines on installing the application, including the plug-ins required. I then viewed the second part of the video which elaborated on pdf entries that lack entries like author and how to transform and edit. I did not seem to encounter a challenge here; however, I am unsure about the reference towards a video. I treated it as a book, but instead of the page numbers, I added the URL in Zotero, which results in the above reference structure (author year, URL). I also noticed that Zotero seems to have added a and b after the year, which appears to be because we reference twice or more to the same document.

The next video I watched was academic paper writing which I used to set up my template for the response papers. This video also explains how to add footnotes when required. This video was also beneficial to enable students to set up the template and understand how to apply the headings.

That was the last video that completed the study material. However, I noticed two more videos on the left side on <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1>. I viewed the other video on Zotero, A Complete Beginner's Guide. The content of this video was similar to the required videos, yet it explained the use with Firefox and had some different explanations on the use of the application, references, collections, tags, and so on, which I found very useful.

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The second additional video was a handy tutorial on Grammarly. This video explained the features of the premium version.

"If you sign in to your Grammarly account, you should be on PREMIUM" (Roshan 2018, at 0:07-0:10)

It seemed I encountered a challenge as I only saw EDU instead of PREMIUM on the top-left side, so I flagged it to the instructor for this course. It seems all should be fine. However, I do not see the "advanced issues" like overused words and repetitive words mentioned in the video. Also, the scorecard mentioned in the video appears to only be available on Grammarly.com editor after I copy-paste the whole text.

As mentioned in the video on the left side of the screen, the options menu does not appear there, so I do not know the settings for document type, contextual spelling, grammar, punctuation, sentence structure, and style. I was unable to verify these settings. Vocabulary enhancements is another setting I could not verify as that button was also not present on the left side of my online editor. I extracted the pdf report on the online version by clicking "See performance" under the Overall Score.

Grammarly is a beneficial tool with perfect suggestions for non-native English speakers like me. It adds considerable value to this course and will drastically improve my output's quality.

Another great asset is the Checklist for Response Papers which I used before sending this response paper. I also encountered a challenge creating the Zotero reference for the corresponding word document. Hence, I converted it to pdf, yet it is still the same challenge as I seem unable to adjust the reference from Zotero and am not aware where the "n.d." can be altered thru Zotero.

9) CONCLUSION

This first session was beneficial to lay a good foundation and reference for the subsequent courses, and the tools provided are top-level and add tremendous value.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 3rd ed. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Roshan. 2018. "Grammarly Tutorial: Making Use of Grammarly Premium & An Overview of Grammarly for Google Docs". October 17, 2018. YouTube video, 7:29. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FKRBvTOLo1M>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

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